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Corresponding Author:

Dr. Tanveer Hussain
Mughal, CMH Rawalakot
AJK
tanveerhussainmughal517
@gmail.com

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**PREVALENCE OF USING CONTACT
LENSES AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS**

AUTHORS:

1. DR. TANVEER HUSSAIN MUGHAL, CMH
RAWALAKOT AJK
2. DR. SAFEER BUTT, CMH RAWALAKOT AJK

ABSTRACT:

The prevalence of refractive problems in the eyes is increasing around the world. For more than a century, contact lenses (CLs) have been prescribed for the correction of refractive defects, cosmetic purposes, and as a treatment modality for corneal diseases. This descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out among the medical students wearing glasses for eyesight. The data was analyzed using Microsoft Excel Office 365. A total of 290 medical students wearing glasses were included in this study. There were 131 (45.17%) males and 159 (54.83%) females. Among the students wearing glasses, 78 (26.90%) use contact lenses occasionally and 212 (73.10%) don't use contact lenses.

Keywords: Contact Lenses

INTRODUCTION:

In the world, the prevalence of refractive problems of the eyes is increasing. Contact lenses (CLs) have been prescribed for the correction of refractive defects, for cosmetic purposes, and as a treatment modality for corneal diseases for more than a century. The use of CLs has expanded significantly in recent years, and an even greater increase is projected in the future. CLs are a safe and effective method of vision correction if they are maintained in the proper manner as prescribed. Wearers of CLs, on the other hand, may be at risk of developing eye infections if they do not properly wear, clean, disinfect, and store their CLs. According to a 2016 survey, almost 41 million inhabitants of the United States wear CLs, and more than 99 percent of them reported engaging in at least one behavior that put them at risk of developing an eye infection.

A survey conducted in 2013 among CL fitters from 40 counties (from 2007 to 2011) revealed a significant growth in the use of disposable lenses generally, as demonstrated by the results of the study. The increasing number of CLs users has resulted in an increase in the number of problems associated with their use. Symptoms such as burning, stinging, and crying eyes were noted among those who continued to use CLs, according to a study conducted in the United States, and dry eyes were frequently mentioned among adolescent participants. A survey conducted in Riyadh to determine the incidence and awareness of CLs usage among female university students and those who frequent beauty salons indicated that 38.7% of those who used CLs did so without contacting an eye-care professional (1-3). For information on the prevalence of CL use, as well as the associated behavioral risk factors and repercussions, epidemiological studies are required. However, little is known regarding the existence of such an issue among medical students in Pakistan. As a result, such research is required.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out among the medical students wearing glasses for eyesight. A simple questionnaire containing name, age, gender, use of contact lenses was prepared. The data was analyzed using Microsoft Excel Office 365. The quantitative variables were presented in the form of a mean and a standard deviation. The qualitative variables were presented in the form of frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

A total of 290 medical students wearing glasses were included in this study. There were 131 (45.17%) males and 159 (54.83%) females. Among the students wearing glasses, 78 (26.90%) use contact lenses occasionally and 212 (73.10%) don't use contact lenses.

DISCUSSION:

Contact lenses are generally safe if they are used correctly. Complications from contact lens wear affect roughly 5% of wearers yearly. Factors leading to eye damage varies, and improper use of a contact lens may affect the eyelid, the conjunctiva, and, most of all, the whole structure of the cornea. Poor lens care can lead to infections by various microorganisms including bacteria, fungi, and Acanthamoeba (Acanthamoeba keratitis).

Many complications arise when contact lenses are worn not as prescribed (improper wear schedule or lens replacement). Sleeping in lenses not designed or approved for extended wear is a common cause of complications. Many people go too long before replacing their contacts, wearing lenses designed for 1, 14, or 30 days of wear for multiple months or years. While this does save on the cost of lenses, it risks permanent damage to the eye and even loss of sight. For non-Silicone-Hydrogel lenses, one of the major factors that causes complications is that the contact lens is an oxygen barrier. The cornea needs a constant supply of oxygen to remain completely transparent and function as it should; it normally gets that oxygen from the surrounding air while

awake, and from the blood vessels in the back of the eyelid while asleep. The most prominent risks associated with long-term, chronic low oxygen to the cornea include corneal neovascularization, increased epithelial permeability, bacterial adherence, microcysts, corneal edema, endothelial polymegethism, dry eye and potential increase in myopia. Much of the research into soft and rigid contact lens materials has centered on improving oxygen transmission through the lens. Silicone-Hydrogel lenses available today have effectively eliminated hypoxia for most patients.

Mishandling of contact lenses can also cause problems. Corneal abrasions can increase the chances of infection. When combined with improper cleaning and disinfection of the lens, a risk of infection further increases. Decreased corneal sensitivity after extended contact lens wear may cause a patient to miss some of the earliest symptoms of such complications (4-5).

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